

FUTURE ESTIMATION OF HYDROMETEOROLOGICAL VARIABLES USING MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES: A COMPARATIVE APPROACH

Jean Firmino Cardoso ¹

Erickson Johny Galindo da Silva ²

Ialy Rayane de Aguiar Costa ³

Andreia Azevedo Abrantes de Oliveira ⁴

Artur Paiva Coutinho ⁵

Saulo de Tarso Marques Bezerra ⁶

ABSTRACT

Objective: The objective of the research was to analyze and compare different machine learning models to identify which technique presents the best performance in predicting hydrometeorological variables.

Theoretical Framework: This section presents the main concepts that underpin the work. Machine learning techniques such as support vector machines, decision trees, random forests, artificial neural networks, and gradient boosting are presented, providing a solid foundation for understanding the context of the investigation.

Method: The study uses a comparative methodology by applying machine learning techniques to predict hydrometeorological variables based on data collected in Petrolina-PE. Various machine learning techniques were employed and compared. Data normalization was performed through logarithms, and the treatment included filling or excluding inconsistent records. The effectiveness of the models is evaluated using metrics such as the Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency coefficient, Willmott index, and Pearson correlation coefficient.

Results and Discussion: The obtained results showed good predictability, ranging from 50 to 70% efficiency. The comparative analysis of the results allowed identifying patterns and relationships between variables and initial configurations of the algorithms, contributing to a better understanding of hydrometeorological processes and their predictability.

Research Implications: By providing more accurate and reliable forecasts, the models presented can assist managers in making decisions about the sustainable use of water and the mitigation of natural disasters such as floods.

Originality/Value: This study contributes to the literature by advancing the estimation of hydrometeorological variables, improving existing techniques, and providing more accurate data for water resource management. Its impact extends from mitigating risks associated with extreme hydrological events to promoting efficiency in the use of water resources, contributing to the sustainability and resilience of aquatic ecosystems, essential in the face of climate change and environmental challenges.

¹ Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Caruaru, Pernambuco, Brazil. E-mail: jean.firmino@ufpe.br
Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6092-713X>

² Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Caruaru, Pernambuco, Brazil. E-mail: erickson.galindo@ufpe.br
Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8738-9981>

³ Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Caruaru, Pernambuco, Brazil. E-mail: ialy.costa@ufpe.br
Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6655-487X>

⁴ Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Caruaru, Pernambuco, Brazil. E-mail: andreia.abrantes@ufpe.br
Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2002-3766>

⁵ Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Caruaru, Pernambuco, Brazil. E-mail: arthur.coutinho@ufpe.br
Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0644-0037>

⁶ Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Caruaru, Pernambuco, Brazil. E-mail: saulo.tarso@ufpe.br
Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5815-5908>

Keywords: Hydrometeorology, Machine Learning, River Flow, Water Resources, Computational Models.

ESTIMATIVA FUTURA DE VARIÁVEIS HIDROMETEOROLÓGICAS UTILIZANDO TÉCNICAS DE APRENDIZAGEM DE MÁQUINA: UMA ABORDAGEM COMPARATIVA

RESUMO

Objetivo: O objetivo da pesquisa foi analisar e comparar diferentes modelos de aprendizagem de máquina para identificar qual técnica apresenta o melhor desempenho na previsão de variáveis hidrometeorológicas.

Referencial Teórico: Neste tópico, são apresentados os principais conceitos que fundamentam o trabalho. As técnicas de aprendizagem de máquina, como máquinas de suporte vetorial, árvore de decisão, florestas aleatórias, redes neurais artificiais e reforço de gradiente são apresentadas, fornecendo uma base sólida para a compreensão do contexto da investigação.

Método: O estudo utiliza uma metodologia comparativa aplicando técnicas de aprendizado de máquina para prever variáveis hidrometeorológicas, baseando-se em dados coletados em Petrolina-PE. Diversas técnicas de aprendizagem de máquina foram empregadas e comparadas. A normalização dos dados foi realizada através de logaritmos, e o tratamento incluiu preenchimento ou exclusão de registros inconsistentes. A eficácia dos modelos é avaliada usando métricas como o coeficiente de eficiência de Nash-Sutcliffe, índice de Willmott e coeficiente de correlação de Pearson.

Resultados e Discussão: Os resultados obtidos apresentaram uma capacidade de previsibilidade boa, variando de 50 a 70% sua eficiência. A análise comparativa dos resultados permitiu identificar padrões e relações entre variáveis e configurações iniciais dos algoritmos, contribuindo para uma melhor compreensão dos processos hidrometeorológicos e sua previsibilidade.

Implicações da Pesquisa: Ao fornecer previsões mais precisas e confiáveis, os modelos apresentados podem auxiliar os gestores na tomada de decisões sobre o uso sustentável da água e a mitigação de desastres naturais, como inundações.

Originalidade/Valor: Este estudo contribui para a literatura ao avançar na estimativa de variáveis hidrometeorológicas, aprimorando técnicas existentes e fornecendo dados mais precisos para a gestão de recursos hídricos. Seu impacto se estende desde a mitigação de riscos associados a eventos hidrológicos extremos até a promoção da eficiência no uso dos recursos hídricos, contribuindo para a sustentabilidade e resiliência dos ecossistemas aquáticos, essenciais frente às mudanças climáticas e desafios ambientais.

Palavras-chave: Hidrometeorologia, Aprendizagem de Máquina, Vazão de Rios, Recursos Hídricos, Modelos Computacionais.

SELECCIÓN DE PROVEEDORES DE LA INDUSTRIA DE LA SAL CON EL MÉTODO DE AHP Y TOPIS

RESUMEN

Propósito: Este estudio tiene como objetivo identificar los criterios para seleccionar a los proveedores de sal y proponer un marco de selección de proveedores para que la industria de la sal pueda comprar materias primas de acuerdo con las normas y precios especificados.

Referencia teórica: Esta investigación sintetiza los criterios de selección de proveedores a partir de la literatura.

Método: Se construyó un marco de toma de decisiones para la selección de proveedores mediante la integración del PAH con TOPSIS. Los datos se recopilaron a través de entrevistas con profesionales de la industria de la sal y de observaciones de la fabricación de sal y la cadena de suministro. El peso de los criterios para seleccionar al proveedor de sal se determinó mediante el uso de cuestionarios que utilizaron la metodología AHP y TOPSIS.

Resultado y conclusión: Los hallazgos de este estudio ofrecen a la industria de la sal información valiosa sobre los factores que deben tenerse en cuenta al seleccionar proveedores, como la calidad, el servicio, la entrega, la

flexibilidad y la capacidad de respuesta. El resultado del método AHP indica que el criterio con la clasificación más alta es la calidad. Los resultados sugieren que los criterios se clasifican en orden descendente de importancia, con la calidad teniendo el mayor peso, seguido de la entrega, la capacidad de respuesta, la flexibilidad y el servicio. Se ha elegido al proveedor A, con la clasificación más alta.

Implicaciones de la investigación: El marco desarrollado en este artículo utiliza solo cinco criterios y fue validado en una empresa de sal. Se puede continuar con la investigación añadiendo nuevos criterios y validándolos en varias industrias de la sal. Se espera que el algoritmo y los resultados de esta investigación se utilicen como insumos en el diseño de la cadena de suministro digital de la industria de la sal. Además, la administración puede usar este método para elegir proveedores de materias primas en función de la calidad, el servicio, la entrega, la flexibilidad y la capacidad de respuesta. La mayoría de los productores de materias primas salinas en Indonesia son agricultores salineros, la mayoría de los cuales todavía utilizan métodos tradicionales de producción y almacenamiento de sal. Se espera que los resultados de esta investigación puedan proporcionar información a los proveedores de sal, incluidos los productores de sal, sobre los criterios que deben cumplirse para que la sal producida pueda venderse inmediatamente a la industria de la sal.

Originalidad/valor: Este estudio desarrolla un sistema de selección de proveedores diseñado para el negocio de la sal, que tiene una importancia significativa en Indonesia. Se prevé que los resultados del estudio de literatura de este estudio proporcionen información valiosa para los académicos que investigan la selección de proveedores. Esta investigación puede profundizarse examinando el impacto de esta decisión del proveedor en el rendimiento de la cadena de suministro de sal, que se extiende desde la fase ascendente hasta la descendente.

Palabras clave: Industria de la sal, Selección de proveedores, Cadena de suministro, Calidad, Servicio.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The prediction and estimation of hydrometeorological variables play a crucial role in the sustainable management of water resources. This information is essential for planning and decision making in a variety of areas, such as water resource management, agriculture, flood control and power generation. However, the complex and nonlinear characteristics of hydrological processes pose a significant challenge to the modeling and accurate prediction of these variables.

The complex interaction between natural factors, such as precipitation, evaporation, infiltration and runoff, makes it difficult to create robust models. Furthermore, the influence of human activities, such as urbanization and deforestation, complicates studies even more. The spatial and temporal variability of these phenomena requires sophisticated approaches to accurately capture changes over time.

Several studies have been conducted in the field of estimating hydrometeorological variables using machine learning techniques. For example, Liang *et al.* (2018) integrated the random forest precipitation generator into SWAT to *perform long-term flow forecasts in a basin*. Huang *et al.* (2019) combined multiple data-based models for long-term forecasts of

monthly outflows using the Bayesian mean. Prieto *et al.* (2019) used random forest techniques to predict flow in unmonitored basins, with the application of statistical tests to assess the adequacy of results. Dayal *et al.* (2021) have proposed an approach based on satellite imagery and machine learning techniques to estimate river flow in monsoon regions of India. Senocak *et al.* (2023) and Valipour *et al.* (2024) applied machine learning techniques to predict precipitation.

Machine learning techniques have been widely explored as a promising approach to future river flow estimation and other hydrometeorological variables (Nachappa *et al.*, 2020). Machine learning involves building and training computer models capable of identifying patterns and relationships in data sets (Braz, 2023). These models are commonly used for predicting and estimating new data.

In this work, a comparative approach is proposed for the future estimation of hydrometeorological variables using machine learning techniques. The objective is to analyze and compare different machine learning models applied to hydrometeorological datasets, in order to identify which technique or combination of techniques has the best performance in forecasting these variables.

This research is relevant and justified by the need to advance knowledge in the area of hydrometeorological estimation, seeking to improve the techniques currently used and to provide more precise information for the management of water resources. By obtaining more reliable forecasts of precipitation, temperature, air humidity, wind speed and other variables, it is possible to improve decision-making regarding sustainable water use and mitigation of natural disasters such as floods. The potential impact of this work ranges from reducing risks and damage caused by extreme hydrological events to optimizing the use of water resources, promoting the sustainability and resilience of hydrological systems.

2 THEORETICAL FRAME

In the contemporary setting of data analysis and machine learning, the SVMR. (*Support Vector Machine Regression*) machine emerges as a robust and versatile approach to the modeling of regression problems, being a natural extension Vector Support Machine (SVM), a technique renowned for its effectiveness in solving classification problems (Lal & Datta, 2019). By adapting the principles of SVM to the regression task, SVMR. offers a powerful solution for estimating continuous values, demonstrating its applicability across a wide range of fields. Its rationale rests on the central concept of finding an optimal regression hyperplane that best

fits the observed data, while maximizing the margin between the data points and the regression hyperplane, favoring the generalization and robustness of the model (Lal & Datta, 2019). Distinctively, SVMR. is able to deal with outliers and nonlinearities effectively, resulting in more flexible regression models that are adaptable to different contexts, as well as offering the possibility to deal with high-dimensional problems, where the relationship between variables can be intricate and difficult to model by traditional methods (Dalla Torre *et al.*, 2024).

Decision Tree Regression stands out in data analysis and machine learning as an effective technique for predicting continuous values (*Decision Tree Regression*). Using a hierarchical tree structure, this approach provides intuitive and powerful modeling of the complex relationships between independent variables and the output variable. The Decision Tree is represented graphically as a flowchart that divides the data into smaller segments, where each branch corresponds to a division criterion based on a predictor variable. The final nodes of the tree contain the predictions of continuous values, allowing the creation of non-linear models that capture nuances and interactions between variables (Latif & Ahmed, 2023).

Random Forest Regression (*Random Forest Regression*) excels in data analysis and prediction of continuous values as an advanced machine learning approach. This technique, an extension of Decision Trees, aims to overcome limitations and improve prediction accuracy by combining multiple independent trees into one robust model (Chen *et al.*, 2020). Each tree is constructed based on a random sample of training data and uses a random selection of predictor variables in each division, reducing the tendency to *overfitting* and increasing model stability. Widely applied in several domains, Random Forest Regression is especially effective in complex, heterogeneous, and high-dimensional data sets, where the linearity of the relationships between variables is limited and interactions between predictors are difficult to model by traditional linear regression techniques (Antoniadis *et al.*, 2021).

Regression by *Gradient Boosting*, an advanced machine learning technique, *has stood out as a powerful approach to accurate prediction of continuous values across multiple domains, being part of the family of ensemble algorithms* (Xu. This method is particularly effective in scenarios where the complexity of the relationships between predictor variables and response variables requires more sophisticated modeling. According to Xu *et al.* (2023), *Gradient Boosting* operates sequentially, combining several weak models, such as shallow decision trees, to form a strong model. With each iteration, new trees are adjusted to correct the residual errors left by the previous ones, prioritizing the cases that are more difficult to predict. The algorithm seeks to find the direction in the parameter space that most reduces the residual error by adding subsequent trees in order to minimize this error, resulting in a gradual and

refined approximation of the target function.

Artificial Neural Networks (*Artificial Neural Networks*, ANN) have stood out as one of the most powerful and versatile approaches in the field of machine learning and data analysis, being widely used to model complex relationships between predictor variables and continuous response variables. These are computational models inspired by the structure and functioning of the human brain, composed of layers of interconnected neurons, allowing for the non-linear transformation of data through hidden layers. The flexibility inherent in ANNs allows for the capture of non-linear patterns and subtle interactions in the data, making them valuable in many applications. In ANN regression, the objective is to estimate a functional relationship between the predictor variables and the continuous response variable, optimizing the weights and bias of the connections between neurons through algorithms such as the descending gradient, to minimize the difference between the network predictions and the actual values of the response variable (Alaneme & Mbadike, 2019).

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 FIELD OF STUDY

Data were selected from Petrolina municipality. Located in the Sertão Pernambuco, Northeastern Brazil (Figure 1), the city is recognized as one of the country's main centers of irrigated fruit growing. Petrolina is one of the national leaders in fruit production, especially grapes, mangoes and guavas, which are exported to several countries, including markets in Europe and the United States. The city is known for the production of high quality wines, favored by semi-arid climate and efficient irrigation techniques, being one of the few regions in Brazil that can produce table wines and sparkling wines competitive in the international market.

Figure 1

Location of the municipality of Petrolina-PE

The data collection point in Petrolina is identified as A307-INMET, and is positioned geographically at latitude -9,388, longitude -40,523 and altitude 372.72 m. The historical series records were started in February 2003 and extend until January 2023, with hourly measurements covering parameters such as the date of measurement, time of measurement, total precipitation for the time interval, atmospheric pressure at season level, reduced atmospheric pressure at sea level, maximum atmospheric pressure in the time interval, minimum atmospheric pressure in the time interval, global radiation, air temperature in the dry bulb, air temperature in dew point, maximum hourly temperature, minimum temperature, temperature in dew point, minimum

temperature in dew point, relative air humidity, maximum relative humidity, minimum relative humidity, wind direction average wind speed, maximum speed, among other parameters.

3.2 DATA PROCESSING

Initially, the strategy was adopted to fill in time records that contained data inconsistent with reality, replacing it with the average value corresponding to the respective parameter. This approach was applied to mitigate data gaps. However, it is important to note that this action induced a slight volatility in the results, with a magnitude in the order of 10^{-7} magnitude. It is worth noting that this volatility is due to the filling process itself and should be interpreted by considering this scale.

Records where it was not possible or that did not make sense to fill with the overall average value of the column were deleted in an integral manner. That measure was adopted to ensure the integrity and consistency of the data analyzed. After performing the procedures mentioned above, a total of 122,444 time records remained in the database.

As to the process of adjusting the collected information, Equation 1 was used, which describes the technique of normalizing the logarithm of the data. This logarithm normalization method seeks to standardize the data, taking into account the mean and standard deviation of the natural logarithm of the training observations. In applying this technique, values are adjusted to take into account the underlying statistical distribution of the data, contributing to a more consistent and comparable analysis between different time records.

$$E'_i = \frac{\text{Ln}(E_{i+1}) - \text{média}(\text{Eln})}{Sln} \quad (1) \quad (2)$$

Where:

E'_i the time normalized information for time i ; E_i is the time temporal information in time i ; $\text{média}(\text{Eln})$ the mean of the training $\text{Ln}(E_{i+1})$; Sln the standard deviation of the training $\text{Ln}(E_i)$.

As regards the input and output data of the models, the possible correlations between the variables were calculated and organized using the Pearson method, as outlined by Cohen *et al.* (2009). In order to calculate these correlations, the integrated function of the *Pandas* library of Python was used.

The resulting correlation coefficients appear as matrices, providing a clear view of the relationships between the collected variables. Values close to 1 indicate a strong positive correlation, suggesting a direct relationship between the variables. On the other hand, values close to -1 indicate weaker and, in some cases, negative correlations, where one variable tends to increase while the other one decreases.

To investigate the non-linear relations between variables, the Spearman nonlinear correlation coefficient was used. According to Yu and Hutson (2024), the values obtained range from -1 to 1. A value close to 1 indicates a strong and positive correlation, indicating that as one variable increases, the other also tends to increase, following a monotonic trend. On the other hand, a value close to -1 suggests a strong and negative correlation, denoting that as one variable increases, the other tends to decrease, following a monotonic downward trend. A value close to 0 suggests a weak or null correlation, indicating a lack of monotonic relation between the variables.

3.3 DEVELOPMENT OF THE ALGORITHMS USED

For this study, a number of relevant algorithms were selected for analysis. These include the application of vector support machines (VMS), decision tree (DT), random forests (RF), artificial neural networks (ANN) and gradient reinforcement (GB). This selection covers a variety of approaches ranging from more traditional methods, such as decision trees and vector support machines, to more advanced techniques, such as artificial neural networks.

The choice of these algorithms was based on their ability to handle the complexity and non-linearity of hydrometeorological data, as well as their effectiveness in performing forecasting and modeling tasks.

3.4 METRICS

The Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency coefficient (NSE) (Equation 2) is calculated as the proportion of the mean squared error between the observed and simulated values in relation to the variance of the observed value. The NSE varies between -infinity and 1, with a value of 1 indicating a perfect agreement between the observed and simulated flow.

$$NSE(y, \hat{y}) = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} (y_i - \text{mean}(y))^2} \quad (1)$$

Where:

y_i is the measured value, \hat{y}_i is the estimated value, $mean(y)$ is the average of the measured values, N is the number of records measured.

The Willmott Index (WI) (Equation 3) is a statistical measure used to evaluate the performance of a forecasting model, particularly in the context of hydrometeorological or climate-related variables. WI compares the accuracy of a model to the accuracy of a reference model that simply predicts the mean value of the observed variable. The WI varies between 0 and 1, with a value of 1 indicating perfect agreement between predicted and observed values. A value of 0 indicates that the predicted values are not better than the predicted average of the observed values.

$$WI(y, \hat{y}) = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2}{\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} (|\hat{y}_i - mean(y)| + |y_i - mean(y)|)^2} \quad (3)$$

Where:

y_i is the measured value, \hat{y}_i is the estimated value, $mean(y)$ is the average of the measured values, N is the number of records measured.

The Pearson Correlation Index (R) (Equation 4), also known as the Pearson Correlation Coefficient, is a statistical measure that quantifies the intensity and direction of the linear relationship between two variables (Thieu *et al.*, 2023). This ranges from -1 to +1. A value of +1 indicates a perfect positive linear relationship between the two variables, while a value of -1 indicates a perfect negative linear relationship. A value of 0 indicates the absence of a linear relation between the two variables.

$$R(y, \hat{y}) = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} ((y_i - mean(y)) \times (\hat{y}_i - mean(\hat{y}_i)))}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} (y_i - mean(y))^2} \times \sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} (\hat{y}_i - mean(\hat{y}_i))^2}} \quad (4)$$

Where:

y_i is the measured value, \hat{y}_i is the estimated value, $mean(y)$ is the average of the measured values, $mean(\hat{y}_i)$ is the average of the estimated values, N is the number of records measured.

Moraes *et al.* (2023), with the model performance index (c) (Equation 5), it is possible to test the accuracy and accuracy of the generated results, evaluated with optimal performance for values of c greater than 0.85 and very bad for values less than or equal to 0.40 (Morais *et al.*, 2023).

$$c = WI \times R \quad (5)$$

Where:

WI is the Willmott index, R is the Pearson correlation index.

The Kling-Gupta Efficiency Index (KGE) (Equations 6 to 8) is a statistical measure used to evaluate the performance of hydrological models. KGE combines three statistical metrics: correlation coefficient, variability ratio, and bias ratio into a single measure of model performance. The KGE range is $(-\infty, 1]$, where a value of 1 indicates perfect agreement between the model predictions and the observed data.

$$KGE(y, \hat{y}) = 1 - \sqrt{(R(y, \hat{y}) - 1)^2 + (\beta(y, \hat{y}) - 1)^2 + (\gamma(y, \hat{y}) - 1)^2} \quad (6)$$

$$\beta = \text{Razão de Viés} = \frac{\mu_{\hat{y}}}{\mu_y} \quad (7)$$

$$\gamma = \text{Relação de Variabilidade} = \frac{CV_{\hat{y}}}{CV_y} = \frac{\frac{\sigma_{\hat{y}}}{\mu_{\hat{y}}}}{\frac{\sigma_y}{\mu_y}} \quad (8)$$

Where:

CV is the coefficient of variation of the estimated ($CV_{\hat{y}}$) and measured (CV_y) values, σ is the standard deviation of the estimated ($\sigma_{\hat{y}}$) and measured (σ_y) values, μ is the average of the estimated ($\mu_{\hat{y}}$) and measured (μ_y) values, R is the Pearson correction index.

The Pearson Correlation Coefficient (R2s) (Equation 9) Square, also known as R2 or R2s, is a statistical measure that quantifies the relationship between two variables to the square. The optimal score is 1, with a higher value indicating better performance. The range is [0, 1].

$$R2s(y, \hat{y}) = \left[\frac{\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} ((y_i - \text{mean}(y)) \times (\hat{y}_i - \text{mean}(\hat{y}_i)))}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} (y_i - \text{mean}(y))^2} \times \sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} (\hat{y}_i - \text{mean}(\hat{y}_i))^2}} \right]^2 \quad (9)$$

Where:

y_i is the measured value, \hat{y}_i is the estimated value, $\text{mean}(y)$ is the average of the measured values, $\text{mean}(\hat{y}_i)$ is the average of the estimated values, N is the number of records measured.

According to Nguyen *et al.* (2019), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) (Equation 10) is a statistical measure often used to evaluate the accuracy of a prediction model, such as a regression model or a time series model. It measures the difference between the predicted values and the actual values in the units of the response variable. The range is [0, +inf) where a score closer to 0 is best. A lower RMSE indicates higher accuracy in forecasting.

$$RMSE(y, \hat{y}) = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{N}} \quad (10)$$

Where:

y_i is the measured value, \hat{y}_i is the estimated value, N is the number of records measured.

In order to comprehensively evaluate the metrics calculated for an algorithm as a whole, an expression developed in the scope of this study, called "Sum of Metrics" (Equation 13), was introduced. This expression is defined by Equation 11. The metrics calculated for the algorithm under analysis are subtracted from their ideal values, representing a perfect performance situation. The sum of the absolute values resulting from the differences between all metrics adopted seeks to minimize, approaching as close as possible to zero. With respect to the set of evaluative equations smaller than $N=2$, the expression becomes obsolete.

$$SM = \sum_{i=1}^M |Métrica_i - Situação perfeita da métrica_i| \quad (11)$$

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

From the matrices generated by the methods of Pearson, Kendall and Spearman, some preliminary combinations for testing by the algorithms developed were identified. These combinations were selected on the basis of the calculated correlation module criterion, and those with values equal to or greater than 0.6 were considered. Of all variable combinations, only some of the most relevant results of the combinations are detailed below.

Considering air temperature and relative air humidity as input and output variables, respectively, the results were consistent (Figures 2a and 3a), as observed in the metrics evaluated (Table 1). For most algorithms processed, the NSE oscillated around 0.75, while R^2 remained close to 0.77. However, the SVM algorithm showed a lower performance for these specific input and output configurations, revealing an NSE of 0.40 and an RMSE of 13.05, distant results for the same algorithm evaluated by Kamir *et al.* (2019). Despite this, the other evaluation parameters showed a very satisfactory and consistent performance among the algorithms considered.

Figure 2

Comparison of the actual and estimated values of the output variables. a) relative air humidity; b) air temperature (dry bulb) with an interval of three days; c) relative air humidity with an interval of 3 days; d) air temperature (dry bulb) with an interval of 7 days; e) dew point temperature with an interval of seven days.

Evaluating the relationship between the inlet variable, air temperature (dry bulb) hourly, and the output variable, also related to air temperature (dry bulb) with an interval of three days (Table 2). The SVM algorithm obtained an NSE of 0.072, presented considerable values in the correlation coefficients ($d=0.699$, $r=0.765$, $c=0.535$, $KGE=0.595$), similar to the results found by Huang *et al.* (2019), but with less favorable results for index of determination ($R^2=0,585$) and MMR. (4,293). However, the models DT, RF, GBR and ANN showed more consistent performance (Figures 2b and 3b), with NSE ranging from 0.576 to 0.584, the RF being similar to the performance of Chen *et al.* (2020). These models showed high values in the correlation coefficients (higher than 0.84) and R^2 determination indices around 0.58, besides RMSE below

3, indicating more accurate and reliable results.

Figure 3

Comparison between actual values (blue) and estimated values. a) relative humidity of the hourly air; b) air temperature (dry bulb) with an interval of three days; c) relative humidity of the air with an interval of three days; d) air temperature (dry bulb) with an interval of seven days; e) dew point temperature with an interval of seven days.

Considering the air temperature (dry bulb) as input variable and the forecast of air temperature (dry bulb) with an interval of 7 days as output variable, different models were applied for evaluation (Figure 2d and 3d). The SVM model exhibited a negative NSE (-5,202), pointing to substantially lower performance compared to the other models. Its correlation coefficients ($d=0,388$, $r=0,627$, $c=0,243$, $KGE=0,437$) suggest a limited relationship between the variables, while the MMR. of 12,489 indicates an unsatisfactory accuracy in the forecast (Table 4). On the other hand, the models DT, RF, GBR and ANN demonstrated NSE ranging

from 0.449 to 0.458, with correlation coefficients above 0.67 and RMSE in the range of 3.692 to 3.723. By comparing the ANN model with the same algorithm developed by Prieto *et al.* (2019), both for longer time intervals, we have a very similar performance.

Table 1

Result of metrics for air temperature versus relative air humidity ratio.

Model	NSE	d)	r	c)	KG	R ²	RMSE	SM
SVM	0.408	0.833	0.877	0.73	0.774	0.770	13.059	14.667
DT	0.774	0.934	0.88	0.822	0.838	0.775	8.063	9.04
RF	0.780	0.935	0.884	0.826	0.842	0.781	7.966	8.918
GBR	0.775	0.934	0.881	0.823	0.840	0.777	8.048	9.019
ANN	0.770	0.932	0.878	0.818	0.834	0.770	8.146	9.145

NSE=Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency coefficient; r= Pearson Correlation Index; c= model performance index; KGE= Kling-Gupta Efficiency Index; R²= R square; RMSE= Root Mean Square Error; SM= Sum of Metrics; SVM= vector support machine; DT= decision tree; RF= random forest; GBR= gradient reinforcement; ANN= artificial neural network.

Table 2

Result of the metrics for the relationship between the inlet variable, air temperature (dry bulb) hourly, and the output variable, also related to air temperature (dry bulb) with an interval of three days.

Model	NSE	d)	r	c)	KG	R ²	RMSE	SM
SVM	0.072	0.699	0.765	0.535	0.595	0.585	4.293	7.043
DT	0.576	0.847	0.759	0.643	0.649	0.576	2.901	4.850
RF	0.584	0.850	0.764	0.650	0.652	0.584	2.875	4.791
GBR	0.583	0.860	0.765	0.658	0.689	0.586	2.878	4.738
ANN	0.584	0.851	0.764	0.650	0.656	0.584	2.874	4.785

Analyzing the relationship between air temperature (dry bulb) as input variable and dew point temperature prediction with an interval of seven days as output variable (Figures 2e and 3e) (Table 5). The SVM model presented a negative NSE (-11,042), indicating a substantially lower performance compared to the other models tested, comparable only with the worst case of Dayal *et al.* (2021). Its correlation coefficients (d=0.331, r=0.678, c=0.224, KGE=-0.251) suggest a limited relationship between the variables, while the MMR. of 16.367 points to unsatisfactory accuracy in the forecast. In contrast, models DT, RF, GBR and ANN demonstrated NSE ranging from 0.447 to 0.460, with correlation coefficients greater than 0.67 and RMSE in the range of 3.467 to 3.509. In the combination, the outstanding model was GBR, as well as in Xu *et al.* (2023), this model showed a higher speed for processing and optimization, even using different hydrological parameters in each study.

Table 3

Result of the metrics for the ratio between air temperature (dry bulb) as input variable and relative air humidity with an interval of 3 days as output variable.

Model	NSE	d)	r	c)	KG	R ²	RMSE	SM
SVM	0.181	0.638	0.705	0.449	0.358	0.497	16.044	19.202
DT	0.506	0.815	0.712	0.580	0.59	0.507	12.455	14.745
RF	0.506	0.815	0.712	0.580	0.588	0.506	12.455	14.748
GBR	0.499	0.811	0.707	0.573	0.584	0.499	12.547	14.874
ANN	0.502	0.811	0.709	0.575	0.584	0.503	12.506	14.822

Table 4

Result of the metrics for the ratio between air temperature (dry bulb) as input variable and the prediction of air temperature (dry bulb) with an interval of 7 days as output variable.

Model	NSE	d)	r	c)	KG	R ²	RMSE	SM
SVM	-5.202	0.388	0.627	0.243	0.437	0.393	12.489	21.601
DT	0.453	0.783	0.673	0.528	0.545	0.453	3.710	6.275
RF	0.456	0.784	0.676	0.530	0.544	0.457	3.698	6.250
GBR	0.449	0.795	0.676	0.537	0.576	0.457	3.723	6.232
ANN	0.458	0.785	0.677	0.532	0.546	0.459	3.692	6.234

Table 5

Result of the metrics for the ratio of air temperature (dry bulb) as input variable and the forecast of dew point temperature with an interval of seven days as output variable.

Model	NSE	d)	r	c)	KG	R ²	RMSE	SM
SVM	-11.042	0.331	0.678	0.224	-0.251	0.46	16.367	31.967
DT	0.454	0.787	0.675	0.531	0.551	0.455	3.484	6.032
RF	0.458	0.788	0.677	0.534	0.551	0.459	3.473	6.006
GBR	0.447	0.795	0.675	0.537	0.578	0.456	3.509	6.021
ANN	0.460	0.788	0.679	0.535	0.553	0.461	3.467	5.992

After carrying out the analyzes for various models and input and output variables, it is important to note that for the other combinations tested, no relevant information was identified in the results.

Considering all the results found, combinations involving air and dew point temperature and relative air humidity were identified that were able to generate sufficient performance to be considered in practical applications using the developed algorithms. Unfortunately, results with good precipitation performance were not obtained, unlike Sáez (2018) where most of its best-performing models were precipitation and flow.

When evaluating the values of the metrics, it was found that the random forest algorithm achieved the best performance. However, when considering the number of occurrences in which

each algorithm had a good result, gradient reinforcement and artificial neural networks emerged as winners of the title of best algorithm for the study.

5 CONCLUSION

Based on the analyzes performed using various models and combinations of input and output variables, it becomes evident that certain configurations stood out, providing valuable insights into the relationship between the climate variables studied.

When considering air temperature as input variable and relative air humidity as output, especially in the 0-day time interval, the results obtained by different algorithms demonstrated satisfactory consistency and performance, except for the SVM algorithm, which showed a lower performance. However, for other combinations of variables, such as the relationship between air temperature and relative air humidity with longer intervals, the DT, RF, GBR and ANN models stood out, displaying more accurate and consistent results, while the SVM performed less.

It is relevant to note that although some relationships were identified as moderate or performed poorly, this provided a deeper understanding of the interactions between the climate variables studied. Models such as DT, RF, GBR, and ANN have shown a more robust predictability and accuracy in various combinations of variables, evidencing their applicability and reliability for these specific contexts.

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